

Dynamical Grounding: Closed-loop Control to Evaluate Functional Neural Models, Application to Spinal Pathway

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Abstract—This paper presents a framework supporting enforcement of functional constraints for a range of computational neural models relating to motor control. It builds upon a control structure addressing the tracking problem for a class of neuro-musculoskeletal systems. We illustrate, through a specific example, the manner in which it may be used to investigate functional efficacy of a class of spinal pathway models. Specifically, we assess efficacy of a stretch-reflex model in fulfilling its expected function and compare it to performance to an alternative model proposed here. A discussion of the manner in which the framework can be employed to help constrain a broad range of neural models concludes this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of modern neuroscience is commonly seen as dating back to the late 19th century, with the groundbreaking work from Cajal ([1]), as well as that of Golgi ([2]). In spite of well over a century of active research, there remains much about the nervous system that still lies firmly beyond our understanding. There exists tremendous motivation to advance this understanding, for instance with the perspective of alleviating the substantial socio-economic cost of neurodegenerative (e.g. Parkinson’s, Alzheimer’s [3]) or cerebrovascular (strokes, [4]) diseases. Similarly, advances in neuroscience have long inspired the hope of providing some measure of answer to the question of *what is consciousness* ([5]), helping us disentangle mind from matter and achieve a better sense of what is a constitutive element of humanity.

Difficulties facing neuroscientists in their endeavors stem to a meaningful extent from the superlative complexity of the nervous system; the human brain by itself having been described as *“the most complex system in the universe”* ([6]). It is a large-scale system, composed of about 86 billion neurons, organized in a number of anatomical structures, featuring tremendous connectivity and coupling both within and across regions ([7]), meaningful organizational spatial scales ranging from the molecular to the whole-organ level, and time-scales of activity or adaptation extending from the millisecond to the order of multiple years ([8, 9]). Investigating the brain across this bewildering range of scales has led to the collection of heterogeneous types of relevant information and data sets, from neural population or connectome data, to patterns of brain activity and observed emergent behaviors.

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Computational neuroscience emerged in the 1980s, building upon theoretical foundations laid as early as the 40s, and seeing a rapid development in scope over the past few decades related to the growth and availability of computational power. The development of models (of specific regions, subregions, or neural structures, i.e. *neural models*) and their simulation allows to reconcile a range of heterogeneous data types, exploiting possible complementarities in a concerted manner. For instance, population and connectome data are used to constrain a considered model’s structure and composition, whereas activity data may be used either in a comparative manner to ascertain plausibility of the simulated model’s produced activity (thereby helping assess the merit of assumptions that underlaid model construction), or to adjust the model towards better predicting the expected activity. In spite of the wealth of data available, models considered remain dramatically under-constrained; that is, for any given brain structure of interest, there typically is a lot more that we do not know about it, than we do know. To advance understanding, neuroscientists have come to explore novel types of informative constraints to bring to bear.

Researchers have explored the notion of constraining the considered model to reproduce the modeled structure’s expected function (enforcing *functional constraints*). The approach has received meaningful attention from, among others, neuroscientists interested in motor functions and associated regions. For instance, the authors in [10] adapted cerebellar modules to “control in position” a NAO robot (effectively performing functions of trajectory generation), while the authors of [11] constrain their model to perform functions of trajectory generation and motion control of a point mass to help study cerebro-cerebellar interactions. Note however that biological motor functions have evolved to address a specific type of control problems, mediating movement through the use of sets of muscles and supporting, for instance, control of musculoskeletal systems. This type of control problems presents a number of distinctive, well-defined characteristics (as discussed in [12–14]). How informative constraints that are limited to trajectory generation, or addressing substantially different (and simpler) control problems, can prove remains unclear. Control of muscle or of musculoskeletal models has been addressed ([15]), but results typically directly connect outputs of models of cerebral regions to muscles (with the notable exception of [16]). In biology, signals to and from the cerebrum are mediated by the thalamus and spinal cord, the later in particular being understood to play a substantial role in motor control ([17, 18]). Such considerations are part of a broader

discussion that revolves around connecting brain models to their environment. Specifically, brains develop to function in interaction with this environment ([19]). Studying brain models in isolation accordingly appears counterproductive at best (self-defeating at worst), and is commonly derided as studying “*brains in a jar*”. Addressing this dimension gave rise to the notion of *embodiment* ([20, 21]), figuratively incarnating the considered brain model, appending this model with relevant bodily functions to support helpful environmental interactions (e.g. incoming sensory streams, outgoing motor actions, possible correlations of the former with the latter). Considering models describing sensory-motor loops in particular, the closed-loop nature of the function appears to warrant special attention. Through motor skill learning ([22]), sensory-motor loops adapt to support motion control of the musculoskeletal systems, displaying properties of stability ([23]) and, to some extent, robustness. We propose to approach constraining neural models by: not only adjusting them to support some of their expected or speculated functions, e.g. muscle coordination for a spinal model ([24]), feedforward modeling for the cerebellum ([25]); but in addition, to integrate this function within a closed-loop control structure acting on a musculoskeletal system and assess the interplay between stability properties or control performance in general, and functional expression. The motivation for exploring the use of such constraints, which extend beyond typical functional constraining, lies in that may help disentangle competing hypotheses concerning the role of neural circuits involved in motor control.

In this paper, we propose a framework for constraining a range of neural models relating to motor control functions. Specifically, we build upon the approach in [13, 14], which allows to construct a closed-loop functional representation, including three key elements; **1** control action being exerted onto a class of musculoskeletal systems (e.g. *the body*), **2** descending signals produced by the cerebrum (assuming the form of a control law) (*the brain*), **3** a spinal model affording mediation between descending signal and muscle fiber activation (the connection giving rise to *embodiment*). In later stages, emphasis will be placed on constraining relevant anatomical models to support (parts of) the control law. In a first step, to help illustrate efficacy of the approach, we in the following use the setup to assess merit of a number of spinal pathway models. In a parallel with the notion of *physical grounding* in cognitive neuroscience ([26]), we refer to this type of constraints as *dynamical grounding*.

Though the spinal example considered remains a mean to illustrate a broader contribution, there exists motivation to advance our understanding of spinal mechanisms. Recent advances in neurotechnology have enabled novel interventions for patients suffering from traumatic spinal cord injury ([27–32]), improving our knowledge of spinal structures would directly contribute to such technologies. The literature on the topic provides a number of neuroanatomical descriptions of spinal circuitry ([17, 33–35]). Among other functions, the spinal cord has been speculated to actively contribute to the control of mechanical impedance ([36–40]).

In the following, we build from the result in [14], which relied on a prediction structure ([41]) to capture muscle dynamics, and extend this predictor to include spinal dynamics as well. Further, descending signals are expressed in joint space, abstracting them away from muscle space ([14]), and leaving muscle coordination to the spinal cord. The class of musculoskeletal systems considered features a set of antagonistic Hill-type muscles ([42, 43]). We include within the spinal model pathways representative of the monosynaptic Ia stretch reflex ([17, 33]), expected to adjust mechanical impedance in situations of excess stretch. In particular, we consider the model proposed in [33], and assess its contribution to mechanical impedance in a closed-loop situation using a metric derived from [44, 45]. We propose an alternate pathway model and compare efficacy.

The main contribution of the presented work consists in proposing a novel approach to constrain neural models, *dynamical grounding*, which extends the notion of functional constraints to consider functional expression within a closed-loop dynamical representation of the relevant system. The control framework presented constitutes an additional contribution, in particular in that it directly allows to investigate a broad range of neural models beyond the spinal pathway considered (i.e. additional pathways, cerebral regions involved in producing descending signals, at different description levels). Additional and relatively minor contributions include the proposition of a novel stretch reflex model (whose efficacy compares favorably to the literature in a closed-loop setting), and extending the control algorithm in [14] to provide robustness to uncertainties in the spinal model.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the class of musculoskeletal and spinal models considered. Section III presents the proposed control framework. In Section IV, we apply this framework to the neuro-musculoskeletal model of a human upper limb and compare the pathway models considered. Section V concludes this paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The considered model describes simplified skeletal dynamics of a human upper limb, accounting for single joint-angle movement in the elbow and shoulder (see Figure 3). This skeletal system is actuated by a set of antagonistic muscle-tendon complexes, innervated by spinal circuits.

A. Musculoskeletal Model

Skeletal dynamics are described by the following,

$$M(\theta(t))\ddot{\theta}(t) + C(\theta(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + g(\theta(t)) = \tau(t),$$

$$\theta(0) = \theta_0, \quad \dot{\theta}(0) = \dot{\theta}_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $M(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $C(\cdot, \cdot)$, $g(\cdot)$, $\tau(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Muscle-tendon dynamics are described by

$$\dot{l}(t) = h(\theta(t), l(t), q(t)), \quad l(0) = l_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\tau(t) = \Omega(\theta(t))F\gamma_s(\theta(t), l(t)), \quad (3)$$

where $\Omega(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\gamma_s(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{+m}$, $F \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $l \in \mathbb{R}^{+m}$ and $q \in (0, 1]^m$. Specifics of the skeletal and muscle-tendon models are provided in [13].

Fig. 1: r_{Ia1} as a function of l and \dot{l} . Reference length l_r depicted here is associated with long biceps head (BIClong).

B. Spinal Model

We consider the same hierarchical structure, from descending signal to muscle fiber activation, as that discussed in [14]. The muscle fiber activation vector $q(t)$, $t \geq 0$, produced by the spinal cord to elicit muscle contractions, is obtained by adapting the model found in [46] as follows,

$$\dot{q}(t) = b^{-1}(q(t))(r(t) - q(t)), \quad q(0) = q_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

where $r(t) \in (0, 1]^m$ describes motor neuron activation rate, $b(q(t)) \triangleq \text{diag}(\tau_a(p_5 q(t) + p_4)) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, where $p_4, p_5 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are characteristic parameters and $\tau_a \in \mathbb{R}^+$ represents a time constant. Motor neuron activation dynamics are described by the following,

$$\dot{r}(t) = -k_r r(t) + w_{Ia} r_{Iai}(t) + \Gamma \beta + B u(t), \quad r(0) = r_0, \quad (5)$$

where $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes a descending signal, $k_r, w_{Ia} \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is a nonsingular input matrix, and $\Gamma = I_m - B^T (B B^T)^{-1} B$. The vector $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{m+}$ represents a co-contraction offset ([13]), and $r_{Iai}(t)$ describes the contribution of a range of functional spinal pathways to motor neuron activation. In the following, we focus on a specific type of such pathways, that supporting monosynaptic stretch reflexes. In [33], the authors propose the following functional model to describe a type Ia monosynaptic stretch reflex,

$$r_{Ia1}(t) = g_1 \text{sgn}(\dot{l}(t)) e^{g_2 \ln(\max\{\min\{|\dot{l}(t)|, p_8 l_r\}, g_3\})} + g_4 (\min\{l(t), g_5 l_r\} - l_r) + g_6, \quad (6)$$

where $g_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $i = 1, \dots, 6$, is a set of constant model parameters, and $l_r \in \mathbb{R}^m$ describes a characteristic muscle fiber length. This model is intended to support a function of muscle-tendon protection, increasing stiffness in response of excessive stretch (limiting further stretch, helping prevent structural damage). Contribution of such a pathway to motor neuron activation, for a given range of acceptable fiber length and velocity is shown in Figure 1. Activation produced is a direct function of fiber length in comparison to the reference l_r . For lengths approaching or exceeding this reference, activation produced is intended to help limit extension and protect the muscle. As discussed in Section IV, inclusion

Fig. 2: r_{Ia2} as a function of l and \dot{l} . Reference length l_r depicted here is associated with long biceps head (BIClong).

of this pathway only had a marginal impact on closed-loop behavior. Consider the alternate stretch-reflex model,

$$r_{Ia2}(t) = 1/(1 + e^{-h_1(l(t) - h_2 l_r) - h_3 \dot{l}(t)}), \quad (7)$$

where $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $i = 1, \dots, 3$, are design parameters. Activation obtained as a function of fiber length and velocity is shown in Figure 2; the model was constructed to magnify the response to increasing lengths around l_r , rapidly leading to maximum activation. In addition, (7) was designed to emphasize smoothness, whereas (6) presents a number of challenges in that respect (in particular around $\dot{l}(t) = 0$).

III. CONTROL FRAMEWORK

We build upon the result in [14], which we adjust to accommodate the spinal pathways discussed above. Key differences with [14] include the use of an output prediction structure ([41]) predicting torque produced $\tau(t)$, $t \geq 0$, in response to descending signal $u(t)$ (instead of fiber activation $q(t)$ in [14]), and using a descending signal in joint space.

A. Tracking Errors

The control design relies on a backstepping approach, which leads to the definition of the following tracking errors,

$$e_1(t) \triangleq \theta_d(t) - \theta(t), \quad e_2(t) \triangleq \dot{\theta}_d(t) - A_1 e_1(t) - \dot{\theta}(t), \quad (8)$$

$$e_3(t) \triangleq \tau_d(t) - \tau(t), \quad e_4(t) \triangleq \nu_d(t) - \dot{\tau}(t), \quad (9)$$

$$e_5(t) \triangleq \mu_d(t) - \ddot{\tau}(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

where desired joint angles $\theta_d(t)$ are user-defined, the estimate $\ddot{\tau}(t)$ is obtained from a predictor defined in a later Section, desired torque and derivatives are computed from

$$\tau_d(t) = C(\theta(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + g(\theta(t)) + M(\theta(t)) \left(\ddot{\theta}_d(t) + (P_2^{-1} P_1 + A_1^2) e_1(t) - (A_1 + A_2) e_2(t) \right), \quad (11)$$

$$\nu_d(t) = \dot{\tau}_d(t) - A_3 e_3(t) + P_3^{-1} P_2 (M(\theta(t))^{-1})^T e_2(t), \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_d(t) = \dot{\nu}_d(t) + P_4^{-1} P_3 e_3(t) - A_4 e_4(t), \quad (13)$$

where $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$, are chosen Hurwitz, $P_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are obtained from $A_i^T P_i + P_i A_i = -Q_i$, with $Q_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $Q_i > 0$.

B. Predictor

We define the prediction error $e_p(t) \triangleq \ddot{\tau}(t) - \hat{\ddot{\tau}}(t)$, $t \geq 0$, where the predicted torque acceleration $\hat{\ddot{\tau}}(t)$ is obtained by directly applying Theorem 1 in [14]. Specifically, consider the following system,

$$\hat{\ddot{\tau}}(t) = \varphi(t) + \eta(t, \dot{\tau}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + \gamma u(t), \quad \hat{\ddot{\tau}}(0) = \ddot{\tau}_0, \quad (14)$$

where $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is chosen nonsingular, $\eta(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a smooth function of its arguments, and

$$\varphi(t) \triangleq (\ddot{\tau}(t) - u_f(t) - \tau_f(t)) / \tau_1 - \beta_1 u_f(t) - \bar{A}_p e_p(t), \quad (15)$$

where $\bar{A}_p \triangleq (A_p - P_p/2) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $A_p \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is Hurwitz, $\tau_1, \beta_1 \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $P_p \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is obtained from $A_p^T P_p + P_p A_p = -Q_p$, $Q_p > 0$. The filtered input-output signals $u_f(t)$ and $\tau_f(t)$ are obtained from

$$\dot{u}_f(t) = -\beta_1 u_f + \eta(t, \dot{\tau}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + \gamma u(t), \quad u_f(0) = u_{f0}, \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{\tau}_f(t) = (\ddot{\tau}(t) - u_f(t) - \tau_f(t)) / \tau_1, \quad \tau_f(0) = \tau_{f0}. \quad (17)$$

From Theorem 1 in [14] we conclude that, provided sufficient smoothness of $\tau(t)$, (14) produces a prediction $\hat{\ddot{\tau}}(t)$ that guarantees uniform ultimate boundedness of $e_p(t)$.

The predictor in (14) helps streamline the control design, defining a system that emulates the input-output dynamics of (3)–(5) to arbitrary accuracy (the ultimate bound depending on prediction gains and filter constants). We achieve stability guarantees without requiring exact knowledge of spinal muscle coordination and co-contraction mechanisms (see discussion on addressing both dimensions in [14]).

C. Control Law

Building upon the above predictor, we propose a controller guaranteeing uniform ultimate boundedness of the error $e(t) \triangleq [e_1^T(t) \dots e_5^T(t) e_p^T(t)]^T$, $t \geq 0$.

Theorem 1: Consider the neuro-musculoskeletal system composed of (1)–(5), the following control input,

$$u(t) = \gamma^{-1} \left(\dot{\mu}_d(t) - \varphi(t) - \eta(t, \dot{\tau}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + A_5 e_p(t) - P_5^{-1} P_4 e_4(t) - A_5 e_5(t) \right), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (18)$$

where $A_5, P_5, Q_5 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, A_5 is Hurwitz, P_5 is obtained from $A_5^T P_5 + P_5 A_5 = -Q_5$, with Q_5 positive definite, and the predictor (14)–(17), where we extend (15) as follows,

$$\varphi(t) = (\ddot{\tau}(t) - u_f(t) - \tau_f(t)) / \tau_1 - \beta_1 u_f(t) - \bar{A}_p e_p(t) - P_p^{-1} P_4 e_4(t). \quad (19)$$

Using (18) as input to the system (1)–(5) guarantees uniform ultimate boundedness of the error vector $e(t)$. \square

Proof: with the appropriate substitutions, we obtain

$$\dot{e}_1(t) = A_1 e_1(t) + e_2(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{e}_2(t) = -P_2^{-1} P_1 e_1(t) + A_2 e_2(t) + M^{-1}(\theta(t)) e_3(t), \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{e}_3(t) = -P_3^{-1} P_2 \left(M^{-1}(\theta(t)) \right)^T e_2(t) + A_3 e_3(t) + e_4(t), \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{e}_4(t) = -P_4^{-1} P_3 e_3(t) + A_4 e_4(t) + e_5(t) - e_p(t). \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{e}_5(t) = A_5 e_5(t) - A_5 e_p(t) - P_5^{-1} P_4 e_4(t), \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{e}_p(t) = \bar{A}_p e_p(t) + P_p^{-1} P_4 e_4(t) + \varepsilon(t). \quad (25)$$

Consider the Lyapunov candidate $V(e) = e^T P e$, where P is the block diagonal matrix composed of the P_i 's, $i = 1, \dots, 5$,

Fig. 3: Skeletal system and joint angle definitions, reproduced from [13].

and P_p . Differentiating $V(e(t))$ along the trajectories of (20)–(25), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) &= -e^T(t) Q e(t) - 2e_5^T(t) P_5 A_5 e_p(t) \\ &\quad + 2e_p^T(t) P_p \varepsilon(t) - e_p^T(t) (P_p^2 + I_n) e_p(t) \\ &\leq -e^T(t) Q e(t) + \epsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where Q is the block diagonal matrix composed of the Q_i 's and \bar{Q}_p , and ϵ is the upper bound of $\varepsilon(t)$, $t \geq 0$. From (26), we conclude that $\dot{V}(t)$ remains strictly negative outside the compact set $\mathcal{S} = \{e | e^T Q e \leq \epsilon\}$, which directly implies uniform ultimate boundedness of the error vector $e(t)$. \blacksquare

In the following, we apply the control law from Theorem 1 to a model representative of a human upper limb.

IV. CLOSED-LOOP SIMULATION RESULTS

We apply the proposed control framework to a two degree of freedom skeletal system, descriptive of a human upper limb constrained to the vertical plane (see Figure 3), actuated by a set of seven muscle-tendon complexes. We first illustrate efficacy of the control framework by assessing tracking performance. We then investigate closed-loop behavior of the considered monosynaptic Ia reflex models.

A. Trajectory Tracking

To assess performance, we simulate tracking of a sinusoidal trajectory in joint space. We simulate the closed-loop model in MATLAB, using ODE45 ([47]) for numerical integration. The desired trajectory is defined as $\theta_d(t) = a \sin(\omega t) + b$, $t \geq 0$, with $a = \pi/180 \text{ diag}([35 \ 8.75]) \text{ rad}$, $\omega = [3/\pi \ 4/\pi]^T \text{ rad/s}$, and $b = \pi/180 [52.5 \ 17.5]^T \text{ rad}$. Control gains are $A_1 = 4 I_n$, $A_2 = 2 I_n$, $A_3 = 2 I_n$, $A_4 = 10 I_n$, $A_5 = 20 I_n$ and $A_p = 20 I_n$. In addition, $Q_1 = I_n$, $Q_2 = I_n$, $Q_3 = I_n$, $Q_4 = I_n$, $Q_5 = I_n$ and $Q_p = 10 I_n$. The initial conditions used are $\theta_0 = [0, 0]^T \text{ rad}$, $\dot{\theta}_0 = [0, 0]^T$, $l_0 = [10.28, 9.96, 6.78, 6.38, 14.04, 13.95, 8.77]^T \text{ cm}$, $q_0 = [0.03, 0.12, 0.08, 0.08, 0.23, 0.21, 0.29]^T$ and $r_0 = [0.03, 0.12, 0.09, 0.09, 0.23, 0.21, 0.29]^T$. Details of model (1)–(5) are provided in Section V and [14]. In addition, we use $r_{1a}(t) = 0$ for trajectory tracking. Trajectory performance is excellent, as shown in Figure 4. Descending signals are represented in Figure 5. As discussed in [13, 14], the muscle model used ([46]) suffers from a lack of smoothness at transitions between flexion and extension,

Fig. 4: Joint angles (top) and torques (bottom), desired in green, shoulder in blue, elbow in red.

Fig. 5: Descending signals premultiplied by input matrix B for extensors (top) and flexors (bottom). Actual signal (black) and filtered signal is depicted.

leading to the emergence of high frequency content in higher relative orders. It is visible in Figure 5, where we parsed high-frequency content (grey) from meaningful signal.

B. Impedance Contribution of Spinal Pathways

To investigate respective merit of the considered models of monosynaptic Ia stretch reflex, we evaluate changes in joint stiffness in response to prescribed joint-angle steps. The desired elbow angle is kept constant at 10deg, whereas the elbow starts at 30deg, before undergoing a step at $t = 5s$ to desired elbow angles of 20deg, 10deg, and $-5deg$. Note that at $-5deg$, the elbow finds itself in a situation of overstretch (i.e. excess flexors stretch), in which one expects the stretch reflex to produce a meaningful restoring stiffness (opposing excess stretch). To characterize joint stiffness, we consider the following metric ([44, 45]),

$$s(t) = -\frac{\partial \Omega(t)}{\partial \theta(t)} F \gamma_s(t) + k_m \Omega(\theta(t)) F \frac{\partial \gamma_s(t)}{\partial l(t)} \Omega(\theta(t))^T, \quad (27)$$

where the first term describes joint kinematics stiffness, the latter represents the muscle fiber's contribution, $k_m =$

Fig. 6: Step responses; the shoulder is kept at 10deg, the elbow is provided steps from 30deg to 20deg, 10deg, $-5deg$.

Fig. 7: Joint stiffness during step response test. Depicted are excessive stretch response with endpoint $-5deg$ (black), and endpoints 10deg (blue) and 20deg (red).

$1deg^{-1}$. The step response is shown in Figure 6, the elbow's joint stiffness in Figure 7. Muscle fiber length $l(t)$ and speed $\dot{l}(t)$, which determine pathway response, change with skeletal kinematics (as a function of $\theta(t)$, $\dot{\theta}(t)$), but also with higher relative order signals (notably, $q(t)$ which directly acts upon $\dot{l}(t)$). From the limb's kinematics, flexors undergo a measure of stretch across the entire range of joint angles considered. As a result, we observe functional expression of the stretch reflex model across all prescribed elbow joint-angle values in terms of added stiffness, for both the model proposed in [33] and that proposed here. In the situation of excess stretch (red in Figure 7), the model from [33] provides only a marginal increase in joint stiffness, where the model provided by (7) leads to a twofold increase in stiffness over the reference.

Muscle fiber activation is shown in Figure 8 for the 30deg \rightarrow $-5deg$ step, the corresponding stretch pathway contribution to motor neuron activation is presented in Figure 9. The model given by (7) leads to greater fiber activation across flexors and extensors. As clearly visible from Figure 9, the monosynaptic Ia stretch reflex is inactive for extensors

Fig. 8: Muscle fiber activation profiles shown for excessive stretch scenario; extensors (top) and flexors (bottom). $r_{Ia} = 0$ (dashed), Prochazka 1999 (dotted), proposed model (solid).

(top). Change in extensors' fiber activation result from the control law compensating the additional activation on the flexor side, leading to an increase in cocontraction and higher joint stiffness. Although the model in [33] appears sound upon close inspection, its effects on joint dynamics are difficult to ascertain in the abstract. It contributes (in competition with other terms) to motor neuron activation, which itself leads to fiber activation. The relationship from muscle fiber activation to skeletal movement is, itself, nontrivial and highly nonlinear. Only by integrating this model within a functional closed-loop framework are we able to assess effective impact of the reflex on dynamics. Its impact on joint impedance appears limited, whereas the model provided by (7) appears to provide a meaningful difference.

V. CONCLUSION

The presented work proposes the use of a control framework, which relies on a prediction scheme ([41, 48, 49]), to investigate (and constrain) neural models. The framework was applied to assess merit of models of the monosynaptic Ia stretch reflex. The control framework extends that in [14] by relaxing knowledge requirements of the spinal model. Control performance of the control architecture was assessed, and the framework exploited to evaluate spinal pathway response to steps in joint angles in a dynamic setting. A measure of joint stiffness was used to quantify contribution of the considered stretch reflex models. The result provided illustrates the manner in which the proposed framework may be exploited to assess behavior of neural models in a dynamical setting. Ongoing work entails the consideration of a broad range of spinal models, describing different pathways at different levels of representation (e.g. closed-form, neuron population). In particular, we are considering the reciprocal Ia inhibitory pathway, Ib inhibitory pathway ([33]), Renshaw inhibition and presynaptic inhibition ([50–52]). In addition, efforts are being invested in integrating models of cerebral functions within the control law (e.g. cerebellar circuits supporting functions of feedforward modeling).

Fig. 9: Ia stretch reflex neuron activation shown for excessive stretch scenario; extensors (top) and flexors (bottom). Prochazka 1999 (dotted), proposed model (solid).

APPENDIX

For a detailed description of the musculoskeletal model presented in Section II, see the Appendix in [14]. In the following, we provide parameter values of the muscle-tendon model adopted from [46] that differ from those in [14], spinal pathway models, and further details on the predictor.

A. Neural and Muscle-Tendon Model Parameters

Values for F , l_r , l_{t0} and α_r are provided in Table 1 (with values adapted from [53]). Parameters used in (4)–(5) are the following, $g_1 = 4.3$, $g_2 = 0.6$, $g_3 = 0.01$, $g_4 = 2$, $g_5 = 1.5$, $g_6 = 10$, $h_1 = 1.5$, $h_2 = 0.99$, $h_3 = 0.05$, $k_r = 1$, $w_{Ia} = 0.5$. To obtain the input matrix B , we defined a mapping representative of the manner in which muscle-tendon complexes connect to the respective actuated joints based on the connectivity defined in $\Omega(\theta(t))$, specifically,

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 20 & -20 & 0 & 0 & 20 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -20 & -20 & -20 & 20 & 20 & 20 \end{bmatrix}^\dagger, \quad (28)$$

where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the usual pseudoinverse ([54]), $\beta = 0.4$.

B. Predictor

The predictor in (14) is parameterized as follows for the simulation considered in Section IV; $\gamma = I_n$ and the function $\eta(t, \dot{\tau}, \dot{\theta})$ is of the form $\eta(t, \dot{\tau}, \dot{\theta}) = W_\eta \varphi(t, \dot{\tau}, \dot{\theta})$, where entries of $\varphi(t, \dot{\tau}, \dot{\theta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 2}$ are polynomials of input arguments (linear in $\dot{\theta}$ and $\dot{\tau}$, product of $\dot{\theta}$ with $\dot{\tau}$, and constant offset), and $W_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 4}$ denotes parameters obtained from Gaussian regression ([55]) using simulated trajectories as training data. Filter constants τ_1 and β_1 are set to 1.

Muscle	F [N]	l_r [cm]	l_{t0} [cm]	α_r [deg]
Anterior Deltoid (DEL1)	1,218.9	9.74	10.58	22
Triceps long head (TRlong)	771.8	13.38	18.1	12
Triceps lateral (TRlat)	717.5	10.38	9.96	9
Triceps medial (TRmed)	717.5	10.38	9.14	9
Biceps long (BIClong)	525.1	11.57	28.4	0
Biceps short (BICshort)	316.8	13.21	20.65	0
Brachialis (BRA)	1,177.4	8.58	5.4	0

Tab. 1: Muscle-tendon model parameters.

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